

METHOD OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract: *The article analyzes technologies for developing creative thinking of future primary school teachers within the framework of a competence-based approach. The concept of creative thinking, the factors influencing its formation, and the ways of effective use of modern educational technologies are revealed.*

Keywords: *competence approach, creative thinking, primary education, didactics, innovative methods.*

Аннотация: *В статье анализируются технологические возможности развития творческого мышления будущих учителей начальных классов в рамках компетентностного подхода. Освещены понятие творческого мышления, факторы, влияющие на его формирование, и пути эффективного использования современных образовательных технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентностный подход, творческое мышление, начальное образование, дидактика, инновационные методы.*

Today, the content of educational information in the higher education system is constantly changing and updating. Its content should reflect not the logic of science, but knowledge related to solving the general educational, personal and professional tasks of the subjects of the pedagogical process. A modern teacher should move from the principle of subject-based learning to such a restructuring of the educational content that will allow students to independently acquire knowledge and show their personal characteristics. For this, the teacher must be a creative person. Pedagogical technologies are changing. Accordingly, the teacher should

work in the process of his pedagogical activity, based on the concept of personality-oriented education.

The results of our research show that the content of the process of pedagogical influence on students has changed. Currently, subject-subject relations are becoming particularly relevant in the modern education system.

In the information society, the position and tasks of the teacher are changing comprehensively. Only ensuring equal rights of teachers and students in the educational process and creating favorable conditions for their full assimilation of information allows students to naturally assimilate knowledge.

Today, models of cognition have changed, knowledge is enriched and combined with new information. In this situation, the teacher is not required to teach students, but to facilitate their independent acquisition of knowledge. Such requirements for the teacher further complicate his pedagogical work and expand the range of his tasks. The information model of cognition requires the teacher, on the one hand, to use existing knowledge-based models of cognition, and on the other, to master new, additional pedagogical functions, to acquire the skill of mediation between students and information in the learning process.

An analysis of research on pedagogical functions shows that existing approaches in pedagogy and psychology treat the teaching, educational and developmental function of the teacher as the main approach to the educational process.

It became obvious that pedagogical cooperation is fully ensured only as a result of the teacher performing certain functions. Many experts identify the main functions of a teacher in his pedagogical activity. Successful performance of these functions requires the teacher to master knowledge in various fields.

If in the educational process a student shows such qualities as independent equalization and application of his knowledge, this, in turn, requires the teacher to create developing educational situations. In such situations, students are encouraged

to choose the content and teaching methods themselves. Creating a developing situation requires organizational, communicative, and design functions from the teacher.

The formation of students' quality of independent organization of their activities requires the teacher to create situations aimed at their independent research and understanding of the essence of the educational material. In such conditions, the organization of a developing educational situation encourages teachers to perform organizational tasks.

An analysis of existing concepts shows that the pedagogical functions highlighted in them require enrichment and expansion of the scope of application in a new era. The research, organizational, and project functions of a teacher can be integrated into general labor functions. In other words, these tasks are included in the general professional tasks of the teacher, since they reflect the technological aspect of his activity. The communicative and socializing functions of a teacher, expressing the possibilities of personal and emotional impact on students, influence the formation of all subjects of the educational process in a changing socio-cultural environment. In the course of the research, we sought to substantiate that the development of students' creative abilities based on interactive teaching methods and technologies is a pedagogical phenomenon that expresses their uniqueness, manifests itself in skills and abilities, provides them with an understanding of material existence as an object of pedagogical research, recognizes the paradigm of personality-oriented education as an opportunity to manifest their creative potential, develops professionally-personal reflection, defines the behavioral model of all participants in the process of pedagogical interaction.

The development of students' creative abilities is interpreted as their subjective reality in modern conditions of a personality-oriented educational paradigm. It embodies the skills of defining one's own position, rethinking, changing oneself and one's professional position, and removing obstacles in the

implementation of one's activities. As a result of the teacher's subjective reality, it becomes possible to analyze the process of forming his pedagogical competence.

If a teacher begins to act based on humanistic paradigms, the educational process becomes the object of his pedagogical activity. A personality-oriented educational process requires the teacher to find new foundations for designing educational situations for the development of students.

As you know, the personality-oriented educational process has emerged as an alternative to the traditional reproductive education system. Its distinctive feature is the focus on the development of independent, creative activity of students.

Pedagogical activity in the organization of a personality-oriented educational process is directly related to:

- special training of students for a personality-oriented educational process;
- organization of a productive educational environment;
- selection and development of a system of productive teaching materials and didactic tasks in individual subjects, etc.

The theory of personality-oriented education embodies the paradigms of competence-based approach and project-based problem education. These approaches and technologies in the theory of personality-oriented education are characterized by a focus on the development of various forms of creative thinking of students. The introduction of this idea into educational technologies has a special pedagogical value.

The productive didactic cycle is of particular importance as a tool for developing students' creative thinking. This cycle is based on getting a guaranteed result.

Within the framework of the competence approach, the educational process is based not on knowledge, but on achieving a guaranteed result. Achieving guaranteed results in the educational process requires students to master a certain type of creative activity. In most cases, this type of creative activity should be of a

professional nature. Such activities require the integration of knowledge, skills, and abilities, as students creatively use this knowledge, skills, and abilities to perform certain types of activities. As a result of their studies, students achieve their own individual creative achievements.

In the process of personality-oriented education, the primary assessment of knowledge is followed by an assessment of the result of creative activity. In this case, instead of knowledge, skills, and qualifications, the ease or complexity of learning activities is assessed. If students quickly and easily complete the presented learning activities, they also consistently master the experience of creative activity. If students encounter difficulties in completing these learning activities, they should continue the exercises to master the experience of creative activity. It is not the nature of specific tasks that should be evaluated, but the level of independence in their implementation.

The innovations being introduced are of particular importance for the work of modern teachers. Therefore, in order to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of future teachers in the field of innovation, it is necessary to develop their creative abilities. Pedagogical innovations do not arise by themselves, they are the result of pedagogical research, the product of advanced pedagogical experience. This process should be scientifically and pedagogically guided.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the task of introducing newly formed educational technologies into practice falls primarily on the teacher. Due to the introduction of modern technologies into the educational process, the teacher is entrusted with advisory, guiding and educational tasks. This requires special pedagogical and psychological training from future teachers. After all, in the professional activity of a teacher, not only knowledge of the subject is used, but also modern knowledge of pedagogy and psychology, educational technologies, and creative experience are widely used. It is on the basis of this knowledge that

pedagogical perception and the ability to evaluate pedagogical innovations and apply them in practice are formed.

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